

Numerical Study of Fractional Stochastic Convection-Diffusion Equation

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Abstract— This study aims to develop a Crank-Nicolson finite difference scheme for solving the time fractional stochastic convection-diffusion equation. The equation incorporates both fractional time derivatives and stochastic terms. This makes it more complex than the traditional convection-diffusion equations. The study focuses on analyzing the stability of the proposed scheme. Specifically, the stability is evaluated in the mean square sense. In addition to stability, the convergence of the scheme is also examined. To validate the method's accuracy, numerical experiments are conducted. These experiments also explore how multiplicative noise impacts the solution. The scheme is implemented using Python software, which enables efficient computation and visualization of the results.

Keywords— Convergence, Time fractional derivative, Stability, Stochastic fractional convection-diffusion equation, Multiplicative noise etc.

I. INTRODUCTION

The convection-diffusion (C-D) equation captures the combined influence of convection and diffusion on processes like mass, heat, and momentum transfer. This equation is fundamental to many physical phenomena, including heat transport, fluid flow in porous materials, and the dispersion of contaminants in fluids, such as thermal pollution in rivers[1]. Stochastic partial differential equations are instrumental in describing the evolution of dynamic systems and find applications in diverse fields such as environmental science, engineering biology, and finance. The stochastic C-D equation, a fundamental building block for more intricate models, is utilized in weather forecasting, studying biomass concentration dynamics, and modeling the progression of groundwater pollution[2]-[3]. Claudia Trauch and Anton Tiepner conducted research on estimating velocity nonparametrically in stochastic C-D equations based on multiple local measurements[4]. Namjoo and M. Mohebbian used a F-D scheme to approximate the stochastic advection-diffusion (A-D) equation[5]. Soheili and Arezoomandan devised a stochastic alternating direction explicit scheme to solve the stochastic time-dependent A-D equation[6].

Fractional calculus extends classical calculus to include derivatives and integrals of arbitrary (non-integer) order, providing a powerful tool for modeling and analyzing complex systems. Its importance lies in its ability to capture memory effects, hereditary properties, and non-local interactions, making it invaluable across diverse fields[7]. Fractional Partial Differential Equations (FPDEs) provide powerful tools for modeling various physical phenomena characterized by memory effects, non-local interactions, or anomalous behaviors. Compared to classical differential equations, FPDEs offer a more generalized and precise framework, making them particularly suitable for systems with intricate structures or processes that deviate from standard models. Consequently, FPDEs find extensive applications in fields like physics, engineering, biology, and other scientific disciplines[8]. Rania Saadeh used finite difference and volume schemes and obtained solutions of the fractional C-D equation numerically [9]. Changpin Li & Zhen Wang applied the F-D method and studied the existence, uniqueness of the solution C-D-reaction equation of the Caputo-type [10]. Fractional derivatives and stochastic noise together provide a powerful framework for modeling complex, real-world transport processes with both anomalous behavior and uncertainty. The fractional stochastic C-D equation is an extension of the classical C-D equation that incorporates two important features fractional derivatives and stochastic effects. This accounts for anomalous transport phenomena and capture randomness or uncertainty in the system, often arising from environmental noise,

uncertain inputs, or small-scale fluctuations. X. A. Ren and W.Q. Wu utilized the stochastic Galerkin method to analyze C-D processes in concentration fields with uncertain inputs [11]. Farshid Mirzaee et al employed spline approximation techniques to solve the fractional stochastic A-D equation[12]. Guang-an Zou applied the standard finite element method to approximate time-fractional stochastic partial differential equations influenced by multiplicative noise[13]. It has been noted that obtaining an analytical solution to these equations is often extremely challenging. In contrast, numerical methods are highly effective in providing approximate solutions for fractional stochastic partial differential equations. In this context, the goal of the current paper is to propose a fractional-order Crank-Nicolson type F-D scheme (FOCNFDS) for solving the time-fractional stochastic C-D equation (TFSCDE) influenced by multiplicative noise, with an initial condition (IC) and boundary conditions (BC) as specified below,

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha S(x,t)}{\partial t^\alpha} + v \frac{\partial S(x,t)}{\partial x} = D^2 \frac{\partial^2 S(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + \sigma S(x,t) \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x \partial t}; \quad x \in [0, L], t \in [0, T] \quad (1)$$

$$\text{IC: } S(x, 0) = f_0(x), \quad x \in [0, L] \quad (2)$$

$$\text{BC: } S(0, t) = g_1(t), S(L, t) = g_2(t), \quad t \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

where, noise intensity $\sigma > 0$ is constant and $D > 0$ is the diffusivity constant. Now, space time white noise $\dot{W}(x, t) = \frac{\partial^2 W(x,t)}{\partial x \partial t}$ is the second order mixed derivative of the Brownian sheet.

Preliminaries

Definition 1 The fractional derivative of Caputo type, of order α , where $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, is given by: [7]

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha S(x,t)}{\partial t^\alpha} = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^t \frac{\partial S(x,t)}{\partial \xi} \frac{d\xi}{(t-\xi)^\alpha}, & 0 < \alpha < 1 \\ \frac{\partial S(x,t)}{\partial t}, & \alpha = 1 \end{cases}$$

Definition 2 : Any sequence of random variables $\{Y_{nk}, n, k > 0\}$ converges to random variable Y in mean square if [14] $\lim_{nk \rightarrow \infty} \|Y_{nk} - Y\| = 0$.

Definition 3: For positive constants ϵ' , ϑ' , and constants ρ' , a , stochastic difference method is stable in mean square if [14]

$$E|S_i^{m+1}|^2 \leq \rho' e^{at} |S^0|^2$$

for $0 \leq \Delta y \leq \epsilon'$, $0 \leq t = (m+1)\Delta t$ and $0 \leq \Delta t \leq \vartheta'$.

Definition 4: In mean square sense a stochastic difference scheme $L_i^m S_i^m = G_i^m$ approximating SPDE $L_v = G$ at time $t = (m+1)\Delta t$ is convergent if $E|S_i^m - S|^2 \rightarrow 0$, as $(i \Delta z, m \Delta t) \rightarrow (z, t)$, $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$, $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, $i \rightarrow \infty$, $m \rightarrow \infty$. [14]

II. NUMERICAL APPROXIMATION

For the development of fractional order Crank-Nicolson F-D scheme for (1.1), we define the space steps as $h = \frac{L}{M}$ and the time steps $\tau = \frac{T}{N}$, such that $t_k = k\tau$; $0 \leq k \leq N$ being the integration time $0 \leq t_k \leq T$ and $x_i = ih$ for $0 \leq i \leq M$. Let S_i^k be the approximation at the grid point (x_i, t_k) to the exact solution $S(x_i, t_k)$.

The α order time fractional derivative $\frac{\partial^\alpha S(x,t)}{\partial t^\alpha}$ at the grid point (x_i, t_{k+1}) , is approximated in the Caputo sense as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{\partial^\alpha S(x_i, t_{k+1})}{\partial t^\alpha} &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \int_0^{t_{k+1}} \frac{1}{(t_{k+1}-\eta)^\alpha} \frac{\partial S(x_i, \eta)}{\partial \eta} d\eta \\ \frac{\partial^\alpha S(x_i, t_{k+1})}{\partial t^\alpha} &= \frac{\tau^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} [S(x_i, t_{k+1}) - S(x_i, t_k)] \\ &+ \frac{\tau^{-\alpha}}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \sum_{j=1}^k b_j [S(x_i, t_{k+1-j}) - S(x_i, t_{k-j})]\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

where $b_j = (j+1)^{1-\alpha} - j^{1-\alpha}$, $j = 0, 1, 2, \dots, k$.

Furthermore the space derivative $\frac{\partial S(x,t)}{\partial x}$ is discretized as follows,

$$\frac{\partial S(x_i, t_{k+1})}{\partial x} = \frac{(S_{i+1}^k - S_{i-1}^k)}{2h} + O(h) \quad (5)$$

The space derivative $\frac{\partial^2 S(x,t)}{\partial x^2}$ is discretized by second order central difference scheme as follows,

$$\frac{\partial^2 S(x_i, t_{k+1})}{\partial x^2} = \frac{(S_{i-1}^{k+1} - 2S_i^{k+1} + S_{i+1}^{k+1} + S_{i-1}^k - 2S_i^k + S_{i+1}^k)}{2h^2} + O(h^2) \quad (6)$$

Hence, the complete discretization of TFSCDE (1)-(3) as follows,

$$-rS_{i-1}^1 + (1+2r)S_i^1 - rS_{i+1}^1 = (r+\mu)S_{i-1}^0 + (1-2r)S_i^0 + (r-\mu)S_{i+1}^0, \text{ for } k=0 \quad (7)$$

$$\begin{aligned}-rS_{i-1}^{k+1} + (1+2r)S_i^{k+1} - rS_{i+1}^{k+1} &= (r+\mu)S_{i-1}^k + (1-2r-b_1)S_i^k \\ + (r-\mu)S_{i+1}^k + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_j - b_{j+1})S_i^{k-j} &+ b_k S_i^0 + \frac{\lambda}{h} S_i^k W_i^k, \text{ for } k \geq 0\end{aligned}\quad (8)$$

$$\text{IC: } S_i^0 = f_0(x_i), \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (9)$$

$$\text{BC: } S_0^k = g_1(t_k), S_N^k = g_2(t_k), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (10)$$

where $r = \frac{D^2 \tau^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha)}{2h^2}$, $\mu = \frac{v \tau^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha)}{2h}$, $\lambda = \sigma \tau^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(2-\alpha)$ and $W_i^k = W(R_{i,k}) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, h\tau)$, where $R_{i,k}$ is the rectangle $[ih, (i+1)h] \times [k\tau, (k+1)\tau]$ for $0 \leq i \leq M$ and $k \geq 0$.

Hence, the complete discretization of TFSCDE (1)-(3) as follows

$$-rS_{i-1}^1 + (1+2r)S_i^1 - rS_{i+1}^1 = (r+\mu)S_{i-1}^0 + (1-2r)S_i^0 + (r-\mu)S_{i+1}^0, \text{ for } k=0 \quad (11)$$

$$\begin{aligned}-rS_{i-1}^{k+1} + (1+2r)S_i^{k+1} - rS_{i+1}^{k+1} &= (r+\mu)S_{i-1}^k + (1-2r-b_1)S_i^k \\ + (r-\mu)S_{i+1}^k + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_j - b_{j+1})S_i^{k-j} &+ b_k S_i^0 + \frac{\lambda}{h} S_i^k W_i^k, \text{ for } k > 0\end{aligned}\quad (12)$$

$$\text{IC: } S_i^0 = f_0(x_i), \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (13)$$

$$\text{BC: } S_0^k = g_1(t_k), S_N^k = g_2(t_k), \quad k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N \quad (14)$$

where $r = \frac{D^2 \tau^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha)}{2h^2}$, $\mu = \frac{v \tau^\alpha \Gamma(2-\alpha)}{2h}$, $\lambda = \sigma \tau^{\alpha-1} \Gamma(2-\alpha)$ and $W_i^k = W(R_{i,k}) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, h\tau)$, where $R_{i,k}$ is the rectangle $[ih, (i+1)h] \times [k\tau, (k+1)\tau]$ for $0 \leq i \leq M$ and $k \geq 0$.

Therefore, the discretized fractional order Crank-Nicolson F-D scheme can be expressed in the form of a matrix equation, as shown below,

$$AS^1 = BS^0 + C^0, \text{ for } k=0 \quad (15)$$

$$AS^{k+1} = FS^k + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_j - b_{j+1})S^{k-j} + b_k S^0 + C^k + \frac{\lambda}{h} S^k W^k, \text{ for } k \geq 1 \quad (16)$$

where $S^k = (S_1^k, S_2^k, \dots, S_{M-1}^k)^T, W^k = (W_1^k, W_2^k, \dots, W_{M-1}^k)^T, k = 0, 1, 2, \dots,$
 $C^k = ((r + \mu)g_1(t_k) + rg_1(t_{k+1}), 0, 0, \dots, 0, (r - \mu)g_2(t_k) + rg_2(t_{k+1}))$ and

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + 2r & -r & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ -r & 1 + 2r & -r & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -r & 1 + 2r & -r & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots & -r & 1 + 2r \end{pmatrix}$$

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - 2r & r - \mu & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ r + \mu & 1 - 2r & r - \mu & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & r + \mu & 1 - 2r & r - \mu & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots & r + \mu & 1 - 2r \end{pmatrix}$$

$$F = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - 2r - b_1 & r - \mu & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ r + \mu & 1 - 2r - b_1 & r - \mu & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & r + \mu & 1 - 2r - b_1 & r - \mu & \dots & 0 & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & \dots & r + \mu & 1 - 2r - b_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

The final section employs Python software to solve this set of algebraic equations.

III.STABILITY

Theorem 1: *The solution of the Crank-Nicolson F-D scheme (1)-(3) for TFSCDE (11) – (14) is unconditionally stable.*

Proof: We have for $i = 1, 2, \dots, M - 1; k = 1, 2, \dots, N - 1$

We define $E|S^k|^2 = \sup_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|S_i^k|^2$, where $S^k = (S_1^k, S_2^k, S_3^k \dots, S_{M-1}^k)^T$.

Then from equation (11) we have

$$E| -rS_{i-1}^1 + (1 + 2r)S_i^1 - rS_{i+1}^1|^2 = E|(r + \mu)S_{i-1}^0 + (1 - 2r)S_i^0 + (r - \mu)S_{i+1}^0|^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} E|S_i^1|^2 &\leq E|S_i^0|^2 \\ E|S_i^1|^2 &\leq E|S_i^0|^2 \\ E|S_i^1|^2 &\leq KE|S_i^0|^2 \end{aligned}$$

So the result is true for $n = 1$.

Suppose the result is true for $n \leq k$

$$E|S_i^k|^2 \leq KE|S_i^0|^2$$

From equation(2.12) we have,

$$E| -rS_{i-1}^{k+1} + (1 + 2r)S_i^{k+1} - rS_{i+1}^{k+1}|^2 =$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& E|(r + \mu)S_{i-1}^k + (1 - 2r - b_1)S_i^k + (r - \mu)S_{i+1}^k - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_{j+1} - b_j)S_i^{k-j} + b_k S_i^0 + \frac{\lambda}{h} S_i^k W_i^k|^2 \\
& \leq E|(r + \mu)S_{i-1}^k + (1 - 2r - b_1)S_i^k + (r - \mu)S_{i+1}^k - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_{j+1} - b_j)S_i^{k-j} + b_k S_i^0|^2 \\
& \quad + E|\frac{\lambda}{h} S_i^k W_i^k|^2 \\
& \leq E|(r + \mu)S_{i-1}^k + (1 - 2r - b_1)S_i^k + (r - \mu)S_{i+1}^k - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_{j+1} - b_j)S_i^{k-j} + b_k S_i^0|^2 + \\
& \quad \frac{\lambda^2 \tau}{h} E|S_i^k|^2
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned}
E|S_i^{k+1}|^2 & \leq \left| (r + \mu) + (1 - 2r - b_1) + (r - \mu) - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_{j+1} - b_j) + b_k \right|^2 \sup_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|S_i^k|^2 \\
& \quad + \frac{\lambda^2 \tau}{h} \sup_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|S_i^k|^2 \\
& \leq \left(1 + \frac{\lambda^2 \tau}{h}\right) \sup_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|S_i^k|^2 \\
E|S_i^{k+1}|^2 & \leq \left(1 + \frac{\lambda^2 \tau}{h}\right) \sup_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|S_i^0|^2 \\
E|S_i^{k+1}|^2 & \leq K E|S_i^0|^2 \quad \text{where } K = 1 + \frac{\lambda^2 \tau}{h}
\end{aligned}$$

This shows that the Crank-Nicolson approximation defined by (11)-(14) is unconditionally stable.

IV. CONVERGENCE

In the present section, the convergence of Crank- Nicolson approximate scheme (11)-(14) for TFSCDE is discussed. We introduce the vector $\bar{S}(x_i, t_k)$ i.e. \bar{S}_i^k be the exact solution of the TFSCDE (1) – (3) and S^k be the approximate solution of the TFSCDE (1) – (3) at the grid point (x_i, t_k) at time level t_k . Let T^k be the truncation error at time level t_k .

Theorem 2: *The fractional order Crank- Nicolson F-D method (11)-(14) for TFSCDE (1) – (3) is unconditionally convergent.*

Proof: Let $\bar{S}(x_i, t_k)$ i.e. \bar{S}_i^k be the exact solution of the time-space fractional stochastic diffusion equation (1) – (3) and S^k be the approximate solution of the TSFSD (1) – (3) at the mesh point (x_i, t_k) . Then \bar{S}_i^k satisfies the Crank- Nicolson time-space fractional stochastic diffusion equation (11)-(14) we get,

$$\begin{aligned}
-r\bar{S}_{i-1}^{k+1} + (1 + 2r)\bar{S}_i^{k+1} - r\bar{S}_{i+1}^{k+1} & = (r + \mu)\bar{S}_{i-1}^k + (1 - 2r - b_1)\bar{S}_i^k + (r - \mu)\bar{S}_{i+1}^k \\
& \quad + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_j - b_{j+1})\bar{S}_i^{k-j} + b_k S_i^0 + \frac{\lambda}{h} \bar{S}_i^k W_i^k + T_k
\end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where T^k is a truncation error at time level t_k .

Let $e_i^k = \bar{S}_i^k - S_i^k$ be the error vector and $E^k = (e_0^k, e_1^k, e_2^k, \dots, e_{M-1}^k)^T$.

Let us assume that,

$$E|e_l^k|^2 = \max_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|e_i^k|^2 = \|E^{*k}\|_{\infty}^2 \quad \text{and } T_l^k = \max_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} |T_i^k| = h^2 O(\tau^2 + h^2) \text{ for } l = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

For $k=0$, from equation (2.11) we have,

$$-re_{i-1}^1 + (1+2r)e_i^1 - re_{i+1}^1 = (r+\mu)e_{i-1}^0 + (1-2r)e_i^0 + (r-\mu)e_{i+1}^0 + T_i^1,$$

$$E|-re_{i-1}^1 + (1+2r)e_i^1 - re_{i+1}^1|^2 = E|(r+\mu)e_{i-1}^0 + (1-2r)e_i^0 + (r-\mu)e_{i+1}^0|^2 + |T_i^1|^2$$

$$\max_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|e_i^k|^2 \leq |(r+\mu) + (1-2r) + (r-\mu)|^2 \max_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|e_i^0|^2 + \max_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} |T_i^1|^2$$

$$E|e_i^1|^2 \leq E|e_i^0|^2 + |T_i^1|^2 \\ \leq E|e_i^0|^2 + h^2 O(\tau^2 + h^2)$$

$$\therefore E \| E^{*1} \|_{\infty}^2 \leq E \| E^{*0} \|_{\infty}^2 + h^2(\tau^2 + h^2)$$

That is the result holds for $n = 1$.

Suppose that the result is true for $n = k$

$$\text{i.e. } E \| E^{*k} \|_{\infty}^2 \leq K E \| E^{*0} \|_{\infty}^2 + h^2 O(\tau^2 + h^2)$$

From (2.12) we have,

$$-re_{i-1}^{k+1} + (1+2r)e_i^{k+1} - re_{i+1}^{k+1} = (r+\mu)e_{i-1}^k + (1-2r-b_1)e_i^k$$

$$+ (r-\mu)e_{i+1}^k + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_j - b_{j+1})e_i^{k-j} + b_k e_i^0 + \frac{\lambda}{h} e_i^k W_i^k + T_i^{k+1}$$

$$E|-re_{i-1}^{k+1} + (1+2r)e_i^{k+1} - re_{i+1}^{k+1}|^2 = E|(r+\mu)e_{i-1}^k + (1-2r-b_1)e_i^k$$

$$+ (r-\mu)e_{i+1}^k + \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_j - b_{j+1})e_i^{k-j} + b_k e_i^0 + \frac{\lambda}{h} e_i^k W_i^k|^2 + |T_i^{k+1}|^2$$

$$\left| -r + 1 + 2r - r \right|^2 \max_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|e_i^{k+1}|^2 \leq \left| (r+\mu) + (1-2r-b_1) + (r-\mu) - \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} (b_{j+1} - b_j) + \right.$$

$$\left. b_k \right|^2 \max_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|e_i^k|^2 + \frac{\lambda^2 \tau}{h} \sup_{1 \leq i \leq M-1} E|e_i^k|^2 + |T_i^k|^2$$

$$E|e_i^{k+1}|^2 \leq \left(1 + \frac{\lambda^2 \tau}{h} \right) E|e_i^k|^2 + |T_i^k|^2$$

$$E|e_i^{k+1}|^2 \leq \left(1 + \frac{\lambda^2 \tau}{h} \right) E|e_i^k|^2 + h^2 O(\tau^2 + h^2)$$

$$E|e_i^{k+1}|^2 \leq K E|e_i^k|^2 + h^2 O(\tau^2 + h^2)$$

$$\therefore E \| E^{*k+1} \|_{\infty}^2 \leq K E \| E^{*0} \|_{\infty}^2 + h^2 O(\tau^2 + h^2)$$

Therefore from this we observed that for any x and t as h and τ approaches to zero in such a way that $(ih, k\tau) \rightarrow (x, t)$, $S_i^k \rightarrow \bar{S}(x, t)$ as $(h, k) \rightarrow (0, 0)$.

Hence S_i^k converges to $\bar{S}(x_i, t_k)$ as h and $\tau \rightarrow 0$ i.e. $E|\bar{S}_i^k - S_i^k|^2 \rightarrow 0$.

Hence, we prove that the scheme is unconditionally convergent. This completes the proof.

V. NUMERICAL SOLUTION

The performance of the fractional order Crank- Nikolson F-D method is examined for time fractional stochastic C-D boundary value problem. We consider the following TFSCDE,

$$\frac{\partial^\alpha S(x,t)}{\partial t^\alpha} + 0.01 \frac{\partial S(x,t)}{\partial x} = 0.01 \frac{\partial^2 S(x,t)}{\partial x^2} + \sigma S(x,t) \frac{\partial^2 W}{\partial x \partial t}; \quad x \in [0,1], t \in [0,1] \quad (18)$$

$$\text{IC: } S(x, 0) = \exp\left(-\frac{(x-0.5)^2}{0.01}\right), \quad x \in [0,1] \quad (19)$$

$$\text{BC: } S(0, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(4t+1)}} \exp\left(-\frac{(-0.5-0.01t)^2}{0.01(4t+1)}\right),$$

$$S(1, t) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{(4t+1)}} \exp\left(-\frac{(0.5-0.01t)^2}{0.01(4t+1)}\right), \quad t \geq 0 \tag{20}$$

where $\sigma > 0$ is the constant noise intensity, $0 < \alpha \leq 1$. With the help of Python software we plotted the approximate solution using FOCNFDM and exact solution of TFSCDE (18)-(20) in absence of noise term.

(a) Exact solution with $\alpha = 1, \sigma = 0$

(b) Numerical solution with $\alpha = 1, \sigma = 0$

Fig. 1: Exact and Approximate solution of TFSCDE (18)-(20) with $\alpha = 1, \sigma = 0$

Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the surface plots of the approximate solution of various values of sigma and alpha. From figure 2, 3, and 5 it is observed that decrease in alpha contributes the disturbance in the surface of the mean solution. Obtained numerical solution of TFSCDE (18)-(20) for $\alpha = 1, 0.9, 0.8, 0.7$ with noise intensity $\sigma = 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3$ respectively, and the result is represented graphically in Fig. 4. It is noticed that as we increase α , the amplitude of the solution behavior decreases and sigma increases the disturbance in the mean solution.

(a) Numerical Solution with $\alpha = 1$

(b) Numerical Solution with $\alpha = 0.9$

Fig. 2: Numerical Approximate solution of TFSCDE (18)-(20) with $\sigma = 0.1$

Fig. 3: Approximate solution of TFSCDE (18)-(20) with $\sigma = 0.2$

Fig. 4: Approximate mean solution of TFSCDE (18)-(20) with $\sigma = 0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3$

Fig. 5: Approximate mean solution of TFSCDE (18)-(20) with $\sigma = 0.1, 0.2, 0.3$

VI. CONCLUSION

In this study, we have developed a fractional-order Crank-Nicolson F-D method to solve the time fractional stochastic C-D equation. The stability and consistency of the method are thoroughly analyzed and proven in the mean square sense for this equation. The analysis confirms that the method is both unconditionally stable and convergent. To validate the effectiveness of the approach, we present numerical results accompanied by graphical representations. These results demonstrate the high accuracy and precision of the method. The proposed numerical approach is shown to be highly efficient, providing an approximate solution that closely matches the exact solution. In the case of the TFSCDE without noise, we observe a decrease in the solution's amplitude as the fractional order α increases. This behavior is similarly observed in the presence of noise in the TFSCDE. The graphical results further support these observations, confirming the reliability of the method. Moreover, introducing σ increases disturbances on the surface of the mean solution, which highlights the influence of stochasticity on the system's behavior. In conclusion, the method exhibits robust performance in solving the time fractional stochastic C-D equation.

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